

Psycho-emotional and cognitive background in children with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis

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Relevance: One of the neurological complications in patients with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis is a disturbance of psycho-emotional background and cognitive disorders. Due to the lack of a pronounced clinical picture and insufficient awareness in the literature, the topic is topical.

The aim of the study: to study the psycho-emotional and cognitive background in children with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis.

Materials and methods of the study: we examined 70 children with different JA variants aged 6-18 years in the ThasPMI clinic of cardiorrheumatology department, among them were 41 (58.5%) boys and 29 (41.4%) girls. Among them, 23 (32.8%) children had oligoarthritic form, 35 (50.0%) had polyarthrite, and 12 (17.1%) - systemic option. Most often, patients had II degree of activity (46.7% children), I was active in 32 (35.6%) and III degree in 17.8% children. To identify cognitive neuropsychological disorders and assess quality of life, all our patients were divided into 3 groups according to age: younger - 19 (27.1%), average - 26 (37.1%) and older - 25 (35.7%) children.

Results and discussion: In URA, the nervous system includes headaches of different genes, autonomic dysfunction, asthenotic manifestations, cognitive impairment, less neuropathy, compression lesions of the spinal cord and peripheral nerves (tunnel syndromes), very rarely cerebral vasculitis. Cognitive function evaluation found significant differences in only a few parameters of psycho-emotional activity, when evaluating attention and memory parameters in patients receiving and not receiving CS, statistical reliability was not identified. Differences between the two subgroups of healthy children are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) for all four parameters. The reliable reduction in success rates of extended correction tests in a subset of children receiving CS is confirmed by the Duncan multidisciplinary test.

Conclusions: thus, the attention and psychomotor activity parameters of patients receiving hormonal therapy are significantly reduced, which does not allow to exclude explicitly the possibility of their cognitive dysfunction in older age. The regularity of this assumption is further confirmed by the greater severity of cognitive process disorders in older age groups.

Literature:

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